

QUIZ**LAST NAME: LAWI****FIRST NAME: MSHELIA AUTA****PROGRAM CODE : DIPH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Pr. CLEENEWERCK****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 8 and its 'References' feature.

QUIZ: A SUMMATVCIVE ASSESSMENT

- In writing an essay, research topics are vital, do not exist in isolation but rather draw on either; other peoples work, observations, work environment and so on. What should a student do, to ensure an appropriate research topic is developed?**
 - Reading and researching of related works enables the student to acquire knowledge and evidence for the development of good essay topic. In addition observations and situations around work environment can also contribute to development of good research topic, these will also require reading in related field.¹**
 - Consult the course instructor for topics.
 - Review previous essay topics and replicate.
 - Select from library.
- In writing an essay, certainly one cannot cite all the time, then, when should a writer not cite from materials read?**

¹ "ACA-401 Coursepack Period 1.Pdf," n.d: www.euclid.int, 2.

- Writing on a common topic.
 - When reading material is one of the recommended ones.
 - When the information becomes a common knowledge or is repeated in multiple sources, for example chronic alcoholism can lead to cancer of the liver or smoking causes cancer of the lungs.²**
 - If a writer has mentioned it before.
3. **Research is about asking questions and use of facts to answer the question. Therefore, what constitutes a good research question and guide to provide answer?**
- Asking colleagues to support in drafting a research question.
 - Administer questionnaire to come up with research topic.
 - Read newspapers, identify questions and search for answers from the internet.
 - Research is about asking questions, show readers why it was worth asking, such questions can be unanswered questions; from other from people's research work, observations in workplace, and so on. Experienced researchers do understand that research reports are open to criticism and therefore, among others go an extra mile to use relevant data to test and support answers.³**
4. **What is the main difference between CMS and LMS?**

² "ACA-401 Coursepack.Pdf," 29.

³ Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th edition, Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 15.

- Course Management System is abbreviated as CMS, while LMS is Learning Management System. Both are management systems developed by EUCLID to make learning easy for students, on the other hand EUCLID is able to guide and monitor student's developments. While CMS is hosted at <http://www.euclid.int> and its purpose is to manage the entire degree program undertaken by students (i.e., the roadmap). Students can access CMS by using email as login name and password used during registration, this displays student menu; student's ID, course selected, payment status, courses flagged and started, and so on.**

On the other hand, LMS is hosted at <http://www.eucliduniversity.net>, students access this by using email as login and a generated password, EUCLID recommends that LMS password be changed to that of CMS and does not allow use of multiple emails. Once course has been paid and flagged as started, LMS will display the course contents and materials, in essence the syllabus.⁴

- CMS and LMS are both important sites for EUCLID and students' academic progress.
- Once courses are paid and flagged as started on CMS site, that of LMS is automatically flagged and can be viewed by students once login to.
- Once login, both CMS and LMS automatically provides instructions and steps on what students need to do.

5. What are the two types of citation styles?

⁴ "INITIAL STUDENT ORIENTATION.Pdf," n.d., 7.

- Generally, two citation styles do exist; Bibliography and Author – Date Style, (1) Bibliography style: you signal the use of source by placing a superscript roman numeral at the end of sentence to indicate citation of a source you refer to. The number should correspond to the numbered note (i.e., where source listed). Notes can either be listed at end of page (i.e., footnotes) or at end of a chapter or paper referred to as end notes. Of the two, foot notes appear to be user friendly than end notes. In most cases a bibliography list of sources used is listed in alphabetical order at the end of the paper. (2) The second citation style is called Author-Date style: referred to as parenthetical style (in-text), here you indicate that you have used source by placing at the end of discussion an in-text reflected as (i.e., Author, date and page number or page range), all reference list added at the end of the paper.⁵
- In some instances, both bibliography and parenthetical style are used in same paper.
- Foot notes or end notes are used in bibliography style while in-text does not use any of the above.
- Both bibliography and in-text citation styles uses Zotero for formatting citations.

6. What is the difference between research questions and research arguments?

⁵ Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 87.

- In conducting research, research argument is a step further from research questions.
- Each time you ask a question, you are conducting a research, such questions must be worth asking and the one that will attract the interest of readers. While research arguments go further to identify questions and propose convincing answers. Arguments basically consist of answers to just five questions; what are you claiming, what are your reasons, what evidence supports your reasons, what about other points of view and what principle makes your reasons relevant to your claim.⁶**
- To provide convincing answers, both research questions and arguments requires reading and citation of resource materials.
- It is much easier to address research questions than arguments.

7. **What is the difference between qualitative and quantitative research?**

- Qualitative research is more of narrative than quantitative.
- A qualitative research usually carried out to understand social issues or that which students want to answer, the approach can be: explorative, discovery, and descriptive. While quantitative research describes current conditions, investigate relationship, and study cause – effect phenomena. Both involve data collection, analysis, and interpretations.⁷**
- Quantitative research is more of numbers and basically should be presented in tables, while the use of tables in qualitative is limited.
- Some research can have a mix of both qualitative and quantitative.

⁶ Turabian et al., 36,42.

⁷ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008), 5.

8. **In writing dissertation, literature review is very important, therefore what is a literature review and what are the basic steps in conducting a literature review?**
- Literature review makes writing dissertation easier.
 - Reading newspapers and articles are part of literature review.
 - Literature review applies more to the topic on literature review in writing a dissertation paper.
 - Literature review involves the review of topic specific and relevant literatures on the topic of dissertation, reading other peoples works is motivating and constitutes a research on its own. It requires critical thinking, and search for evidence that supports your claim or understands the role of argument in research. Basically, two steps identified in conducting literature review: (1) identify and retrieve literatures and materials; (2) review, analyze, and summarise in such way that it adds clarity, either in support or in divergence to the questions raised in the dissertation.⁸**
9. **What are the differences between response papers and major papers?**
- Response papers are shorter than major papers.
 - Both response papers and major papers are mere academic exercises.
 - Details of response papers and major papers can be seen in student orientation guide.
 - A response paper is a short assignment given to students, usually between 3 – 5 pages, that must be written using the most recent EUCLID response paper template. It is single-spaced and students employ the use of parenthetical (also known as in-text) referencing. The purpose of writing a response paper is for students to demonstrate to the instructor that they are making progress, read materials and be able to summarize.**

⁸ Bloomberg and Volpe, 45,50.

On the other hand, major papers are also written by students and demonstrate better academic exercise, major papers use EUCLID template which is double space and employ the use of footnote referencing. The length of a major paper is between 14 – 18 pages.⁹

10. What is an abstract? Briefly outline its contents.

- An abstract can an entire summary of a whole dissertation.
- Abstract is part of literature review.
- Abstract is a summary that precedes dissertation body and should provide first impression of the contents of the dissertation, letting readers decide whether they want to continue reading and showing them what to look for if they do. It essentially summarizes: research problem; research approach; key findings; conclusions; and recommendations. A good abstract serves as a professional opportunity to earn recognition within the research community.¹⁰**
- Only a well-structured abstract can earn recognition within the global research community.

⁹ “INITIAL STUDENT ORIENTATION.Pdf,” 3–7.

¹⁰ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 168.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.